

DELAMINATION INITIATION DUE TO INTERLAMINAR TENSION IN FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS

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1 General Introduction

The low through-thickness strength of composites means that delamination failure at the interface between plies is a common failure mode for composite structures. Cyclic loading of these structures can lead to damage onset and growth. The majority of progressive fatigue damage models focus on the propagation phase, using strain energy release rates to predict crack growth rates using a Paris-type law.

However, this approach assumes that a crack is already present in the material, and therefore neglects the time spent before the initiation of damage, which in many cases can be significant [1]. Hence these models tend to provide a conservative estimate of the overall fatigue life. Consequently there have been attempts to develop models that can account for both the initiation and the propagation phases. One approach is to treat propagation as a sequence of initiations at the meso-scale, thereby unifying the two phases into one coherent analysis [2]. A recently developed fatigue damage evolution model based upon this approach has been able to provide the material SN-curves for initiation of damage under pure mode II fatigue loading in a moderately tough carbon fibre reinforced composite (CFRP), and has shown that fatigue delamination propagation can be predicted from this initiation data alone [3].

In order to extend this model to mixed-mode conditions, it is necessary to obtain data for the initiation of fatigue damage, firstly in pure mode I loading, and secondly under mixed-mode loading. This research focuses on the generation of SN-curves for the initiation of damage in an aerospace grade CFRP subject to pure interlaminar tension.

2 Initiation Specimen

There are two general methods for ascertaining the through thickness tensile strengths of laminated composites [4]. The first is the use of flat-wise tension specimens, which consist of relatively thin laminates, shaped in such a way as to produce out-of-plane tension, as used in [5]. These types of specimens can require painstaking manufacture and do not represent the true state of material in actual curved or angled components that are prone to through-thickness failures. The second approach is to use curved beams under bending to produce the through thickness stresses, as used in [6-8]. The use of curved beams has become the established method of measuring the interlaminar tensile strength of composite materials, and this research employs the ASTM standard test method [9]. The curved beam specimen and test setup are illustrated in Figure 1.

2.1 Standard Solution

Solutions have been developed by Lekhnitskii [10] for the stresses in a curved beam segment with cylindrical anisotropy, and his solution for radial stress is used in the test standard. Calculating this radial stress requires knowledge of the moment being applied to the curved section of the test specimen. Referring to Figure 1, it can be seen that this moment is $P_b l_o$, where

$$P_b = \frac{P}{(2 \cos \phi)} \quad (1)$$

$$l_o = \frac{d_x}{\cos \phi} + (D + t) \tan \phi \quad (2)$$

As can be seen, both P_b and l_o depend on the angle ϕ that the specimen legs subtend to the horizontal. The standard states that this angle be calculated as

$$\phi = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{-d_x(D+t) + d_y \sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2 - D^2 - 2Dt}}{d_x^2 + d_y^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where

$$d_y = d_x \tan \phi_i + \frac{D+t}{\cos \phi_i} - \Delta \quad (4)$$

where ϕ_i is the initial angle of the legs to the horizontal and Δ is the roller vertical displacement during the test. However, this equation for ϕ does not give the correct value for the angle, and will lead to slightly unconservative values for the failure stress of the specimen. Although the error is only in the region of 2% for the specimens tested in this work, the equation used in this research was

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{d_y}{d_x} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(D+t)}{\sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where d_y is as above.

2.2 Correction for Specimen Deformation

As noted in the standard, the calculations assume perfectly stiff specimens and do not account for deformation of the specimen. For specimens manufactured from an intermediate or high toughness material, significant bending of the legs occurs before delamination failure. This bending means that the angle ϕ is decreased, which has the effect of decreasing both P_b and l_o , and therefore also the moment being applied to the curved section. Without correcting for this, the moment will be overestimated and the subsequent calculation of radial stress will be unconservative. Additionally, the shear deformation of the curved section increases its radius of curvature, which according to Lekhnitskii's solution will reduce the radial stress in the curve.

In this work, a correction for these effects has been applied, and is outlined in Figure 2. Two separate corrections can be computed; for the deflection of

the straight section AC, and for the change in curvature of section CD. The deflection equation for AC is taken from [11] for a beam simply supported at A and fixed at C:

$$\theta_A = -\frac{P_b B a}{4EI(a+b)} b^2 \quad (6)$$

where $a = l_o$, $I = wt^3/12$, so that

$$\theta_A = -CBS \frac{3b^2}{Et^3(a+b)} \quad (7)$$

where CBS (Curved Beam Strength) = $P_{bB} l_o / w$. The value of b was found from the FE model, but could be physically measured at the start and end of the test and varied linearly between the two to find b at any point during the test, as the results are relatively insensitive to this value. The change in curvature of section CD can be calculated from

$$M = EI \frac{d\theta}{ds} \quad (8)$$

where $d\theta = \theta_D - \theta_C$, $ds = R\phi$, so that

$$\theta_c = -CBS \frac{3\pi R}{Et^3} \quad (9)$$

The algorithm for finding the corrected angle is shown in Figure 2(d), and was implemented in Matlab®.

3 Finite Element (FE) Model

A 2D FE model of the curved beam specimen was created in Abaqus/Standard, which is an implicit FE code. In order to reduce computational time, a half model was created, taking advantage of specimen symmetry as shown in Figure 3, which also shows detail of the mesh construction in the curved region, and the boundary conditions applied along the symmetry line.

In order to accurately model the loading of the specimen, the specimen was loaded using rollers modelled as analytical rigid surfaces and contact pairs between the surfaces of the rollers and specimen. The contact was assumed to be frictionless. The model was created using four-

noded 2D plane strain elements (CPE4). The element size was 100 microns for the majority of the model, but in the refined section of the curve, where the peak radial stresses were expected the element size was reduced to 20 microns. In this region, layers of CPE4 elements were replaced by cohesive elements (COH2D4) every ply thickness. The analysis was carried out using a non-linear geometrical static step. The material for the solid elements was modelled as a homogeneous orthotropic laminate with the properties of uni-directional IM7/8552, as shown in Table 1. The cohesive element properties are given in Table 2. The model was loaded by applying a displacement boundary condition to the upper roller and keeping the lower roller fixed. When the specimen was loaded, through-thickness tensile stresses were generated in the curved section, as shown in Figure 4, which also shows the Lekhnitskii solution for radial stresses. Peak stresses for both the analytical and numerical solutions are predicted to occur approximately 40% of the way up from the inner surface, and are highest at the axial centre of the curve, but they remain very close to maximum for a significant segment of the beam. This indicates that delamination failure of a specimen could occur in a number of ply interfaces given that some inevitable variability in manufacturing quality is assumed, but is most likely to occur in the thirteenth ply interface from the inner surface (for this specimen configuration). Although this is a 2D model, it must be remembered that a delamination could initiate at any location across the width of the specimen.

To compare the solutions for radial stress predicted by Lekhnitskii and by the FE model, load and roller displacement data were taken from the FE analysis. This data was used in the Lekhnitskii solution to calculate the maximum radial stress throughout the analysis. This was done for both the ASTM standard solution and the corrected solution as described above. These were then compared to the radial stresses predicted by the FE code itself. The results can be seen in Figure 5 and show how, without a correction, the standard provides increasingly unconservative results as the failure stress increases. The correction used in this work agrees very well with the FE solution for the expected loads and displacements in the experimental section of the work, and was therefore

employed to improve not only calculations for the mean failure stress of the specimens, but also to improve the accuracy of calculated severities in the fatigue testing programme.

4 Experimental Results

4.1 Specimen Preparation

The specimens were manufactured by hand lay-up of individual plies of IM7/8552 prepreg (210×180mm) over an aluminium male tool. The tool was a triangular prism with 45° sloped sides of length 75mm and a 6.35mm radius at the apex of the prism. Plies were debulked approximately every four plies and when all 32 plies had been laid, they were cured according to the manufacturer’s recommendations, but with one hour added to both the dwell and cure times to allow time for the solid metal tool block to heat up, so as to alleviate thermal gradients across the composite laminate. Optical microscopy revealed the manufacturing quality to be good, with no obvious signs of out-of-plane fibre waviness. Specimen thicknesses were taken with a Vernier caliper, and although thinning around the radius was observed, the variation from nominal ply thickness was within the test standard’s tolerances. Specimens were originally cut to 25mm widths from the cured panel, in accordance with the ASTM standard, however due to problems described in Section 4.2.3 specimen width was reduced to 11mm.

4.2 Experimental Test Procedure

4.2.1 Acoustic Emissions (AE) Monitoring

The key point of this work was to identify the number of cycles required to initiate a delamination damage event in a composite laminate subject to pure interlaminar tension. The first assumption was that this initiation occurs during the same cycle in which the specimen fails catastrophically, with a large load drop as observed in the static tests. In order to verify whether this was actually the case, or whether initiation occurred at some point prior to this, it was decided to utilize Acoustic Emission

(AE) transducers to attempt to detect any such event. These consist of a piezo-electric (PE) device within a metallic housing that can be fixed to the surface of the composite specimen. The PE sensors convert displacements on the surface of the specimen caused by stress waves propagating from a damage event. AE has been identified previously as suitable for detecting damage events in composites [12], and has been used as a method of pinpointing initiation of matrix cracks in tension-tension fatigue tests of cross-ply specimens [13]. In the latter case, a qualitative approach to the AE data was employed, whereby high amplitude AE hits that could be clearly distinguished from the background noise of the fatigue test were associated with matrix cracking events. A similar approach to this was employed in this research; *in-situ* monitoring of the specimens during the tests aimed to detect any signs of matrix cracks or delamination onset events. The AE system used was a Vallen AMSY5, which recorded AE data coming from two Pancom P15 sensors with 150 kHz resonance. The two sensors were superglued to the underside of the specimens as shown in Figure 6. Two sensors were used so that location algorithms in the system software could be employed to calculate the axial position of AE hits along the specimen, and so rule out potential hits coming from the cracking superglue directly under the sensors.

4.2.2 Static Testing

Specimens were statically tested to ascertain the interlaminar tensile strength, as per the standard test method, using an Instron servo-hydraulic materials testing machine. The test rig is shown in Figure 7. Tests were originally carried out on specimens with a width of 25mm; however this configuration was abandoned due to problems encountered during the fatigue testing programme. Instead, a new set of tests were carried out on narrower specimens with a width of 11mm. Five of these specimens were tested, and the load and displacement data were used to calculate the maximum radial stress in the specimens throughout the test using Lekhnitskii's analytical solution and the corrected method for calculating the moment applied to the test region of the specimen. Test machine crosshead displacement was verified by using video gauge software to post-process movie files of the tests. A small amount of

horizontal displacement of the top rollers was observed from the video gauge results, and this was accounted for when calculating the radial stress. An average failure stress of 116.0 MPa was found, with a coefficient of variance of 8.4%. The load vs. displacement plots and the associated radial stress vs. load plots are shown in Figure 8. One of the tests was shown (using Chauvenet's theorem) to be an outlier and was not used in the calculation of mean failure stress.

4.2.3 Fatigue Testing

When the test programme moved on to cyclic testing of the specimens, one of the first specimens tested suffered matrix splitting without a delamination, reducing the apparent stiffness of the specimen during the fatigue test. This failure mode was attributed to either the anticlastic bending of the curved section or torsion being inadvertently applied to the specimen during the test due to misalignment of the test fixtures. Because the tests were carried out under displacement control, a drop in stiffness during a test would lead to a change in the load cycle, and the testing would become variable amplitude as opposed to constant amplitude loading.

As a consequence, narrower specimens (11mm) were produced to alleviate this issue, and these were tested under cyclic loading. The tests were conducted under displacement control rather than load control, as this was found to provide more stable peak loads for each cycle. Both peak loads and load amplitude were observed to remain constant throughout the tests, indicating no loss of apparent stiffness, and ensuring the peak interlaminar stress remained constant. The severity of each test was calculated using peak load and displacement data to calculate the Lekhnitskii solution for radial stress as described above, and dividing this stress by the mean failure stress from the static tests. The stress ratio of each test was determined by dividing the stress at minimum load by that calculated for the peak load. Two stress ratios have been used so far ($R=0.1$ & 0.5). The frequency of tests was 3.9-7.9 Hz (constant within each test), and was set in order to give a similar stressing rate for each test regardless of test severity. The tests consisted of three steps; an initial ramp of

2mm/min to the peak displacement (equivalent to the displacement that achieved the desired stress severity), then a ramp down at the same rate to the mean displacement, and finally the cyclic test. The tests were stopped when the specimens delaminated and the load dropped significantly, as in the static tests.

The criteria used to identify delamination onset in relation to the AE data was chosen to be a high amplitude (90-100dB) hit, as this has been used previously in [13] and seemed to be the clearest method of distinguishing damage events from background noise. However, there is little consensus in the literature to suggest that this type of hit must correspond to a delamination event. Additionally, the AE data from some of the tests have indicated potential damage initiation events very early on in the tests. Figure 9 shows a typical plot of AE data, showing the amplitude of hits throughout the fatigue tests. It can be seen that two high amplitude hits (>90dB) have been recorded; one coinciding with final failure, and the other at the very beginning of the fatigue test. This indicates that damage initiation prior to final failure cannot be ruled out in this case. This situation occurred in around a quarter of the specimens tested so far, hence further work is required to clarify whether delamination onset exactly corresponds to final failure, and CT-scans of specimens taken from interrupted tests may be able to help in this respect.

The fatigue testing programme is not yet fully complete, as more data points are desired to improve confidence. However, the data gathered so far can be seen in Figure 10, and shows a reasonable trend. The figure shows the SN curve for delamination onset due to pure interlaminar tension of IM7/8552, taking, for now, onset as coincidental to final failure.

The SN-curves for both stress ratios appear to show shallower SN curves than the equivalent curves for mode II initiation of the same material. This indicates that fatigue damage initiation is not simply a property of the matrix system, but is also dependent on the mode-mixity. The figure also shows data obtained from a previous study using transverse tension (mode I) fatigue testing on the same material system [14]. This again shows a steeper curve than the data obtained here, and

suggests that an assumption of transverse isotropy for the analysis of fatigue damage initiation cannot be made.

6 Conclusions

In order to develop a fatigue delamination evolution model, SN data for delamination onset in a carbon fibre epoxy composite under pure interlaminar tension have been sought. Static tests have been carried out based upon the ASTM standard for measuring the interlaminar tensile strength of a composite, and it has been found that for a recommended laminate thickness of an intermediate toughness material (IM7/8552), the method for calculating the through-thickness tensile strength of a test specimen will give unconservative values, due to the unaccounted deformation of the specimen under loading. A simple iterative procedure has been implemented to account for this, and results agree well with FE predictions of radial stress. A fatigue testing programme has been begun, using *in-situ* monitoring with an AE system, in an attempt to verify whether these curved beam specimens fail catastrophically at the point of delamination onset. The SN curves generated thus far appear to be shallower than has been found previously using transverse tensile specimens, indicating that transverse isotropy cannot be assumed for this case, and are also shallower than the equivalent mode II initiation curves, indicating that mode-mixity is important in determining the number of cycles to fatigue delamination onset. These shallow curves also points to the importance of accounting for the initiation phase of fatigue damage evolution.

Further fatigue testing using this curved beam specimen needs to be carried out so that a power law curve can be fitted to the data for at least two stress ratios with reasonable statistical confidence. The scatter in the fatigue data is on the high side, but this is to be expected given that the mean static failure strength has a coefficient of variance of close to 10%.

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Figure 1. The four point bend test setup with relevant dimensions.

Figure 3. The 2D FE model took advantage of symmetry, and used cohesive elements at each ply thickness in the region of maximum through-thickness stress to simulate failure.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 2. Correction applied to the ASTM standard calculation for interlaminar tensile strength. (a) Specimen deformation as predicted by the FE model. (b) In order to calculate the change in curvature of section CD it is necessary to find the distance b (shown in (c)); this was done by mapping distances from the FE analysis. (c) To estimate the deflection of the leg AC, assume a beam simply supported at A and fully fixed at C. (d) The algorithm used to find the corrected angle ϕ .

E_{11}	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12}=G_{13}$	G_{23}
MPa	MPa			MPa	MPa
161000	11380	0.32	0.436	5170	3980

Table 1. Material elastic properties for IM7/8552 UD laminates.

G_{Ic}	$G_{IIc}=G_{IIIc}$	σ_I^{\max}	$\sigma_{II}^{\max}=\sigma_{III}^{\max}$	E_I	$E_{II}=E_{III}$
N/mm	N/mm	MPa	MPa	N/mm ³	N/mm ³
0.25	1.0	110	82	1.0E06	4.0E04

Table 2. Cohesive properties for IM7/8552 ply interfaces.

Figure 4. FE contour plot of through-thickness stresses developed prior to failure (right). The distribution compares well with the analytical Lekhnitskii solution for radial stresses (left). Note that this comparison is for the shape of the distribution only, at loads which give a maximum radial stress of 110 MPa for both the analytical and numerical solutions.

Figure 5. Maximum through thickness stresses in the curved section of the specimen with increasing load. Without a correction for specimen deformation, the ASTM standard produces unconservative results at higher loads.

Figure 6. AE sensors attached to a specimen.

Figure 7. The four point bending rig. It was anticipated that knurled rollers (shown) would be required to increase friction and avoid lateral movement of the specimen during fatigue testing, however smooth rollers were found to be adequate and so were used in the tests.

Figure 8(a). Load vs. displacement curves for the five specimens tested statically.

Figure 8(b). The radial stress vs. load curves for the five specimens tested statically. The circles show more clearly the failure points. The red circle (closest to origin) indicates the specimen that was considered an outlier and omitted from the calculation for static strength.

Figure 10. SN curves for the curved beam for a stress ratio of R=0.1 and 0.5. Only final failure is represented. It can be seen that these curves are shallower than the corresponding mode II curves [3], as well as the data taken from mode I transverse tension tests [14].

Figure 9. An example of the AE data from a fatigue test. The critical damage event is clearly visible above the noise at the end of the test. The sharp increase in AE activity at around 240 seconds corresponds to the start of cyclic testing, and includes a hit of over 90dB, indicating a possible damage event.